

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ACCOUNT FOR THE INFLUENCE OF THE ECCENTRICITY OF SPHERICAL INSALLATIONS FOR MEASURING THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF SUBSTANCES

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Abstract

To calculate thermal conductivity using spherical measuring instruments, it is necessary to know the heat flux and temperature difference between symmetrical spherical working surfaces. For the case of symmetric spherical surfaces, the calculation equation is well known. In this work, the influence of the eccentricity of the spherical surfaces of devices in calculating the thermal conductivity is theoretically determined.

Keywords: heat transfer, thermal conductivity, spherical calorimeter, eccentricity.

To increase the efficiency and strength of equipment used in various production processes where heat transfer processes take place, it is necessary to have data on the thermophysical properties of the materials from which the equipment and the working fluid are made. Thermal conductivity is the most important of them.

There are different methods for determining thermal conductivities, both stationary and non-stationary [1, p. 19-72]. Recently, non-stationary methods have been used more [2, p. 347-355; 3, p. 12-22]. According to the shape of the working surfaces, cylindrical, spherical and flat bicalorimeters are distinguished [1, p. 77-81].

Let us determine the exact solution of the problem of the influence of eccentricity for eccentric spherical

surfaces. Consider the differential equation of heat conduction [4, p. 30]

$$\frac{\partial^2 t}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 t}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

We solve this equation using the method of point heat sources, where the resulting temperature field is found by adding the fields from separate symmetrically located sources A and B (Fig. 1).

For the case of point sources, the temperature difference

$$\theta = \frac{Q}{4\pi\lambda} \left(\frac{1}{r'} - \frac{1}{r''} \right). \quad (2)$$

We compose the following system of equations

Fig. 1

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{r_m'} - \frac{1}{r_m''} &= \frac{1}{d - r_m'} - \frac{1}{d + r_m''} \\ r_m'' - r_m' &= 2(h - r) \\ r_m'' + r_m' &= 2Y_0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Here $Y_0 = h - a'$.

Solving this system of equations with respect to h and H we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{R^6}{(a'')^2} - \frac{r^6}{(a')^2} \right] + 2 \left(\frac{R^5}{a''} + \frac{r^5}{a'} \right) - (R^4 - r^4) - 2(a''R^3 + a'r^3) + [(a'')^2R^2 + (a')^2r^2] - \\ & - 2a^2 \left(\frac{R^3}{a''} + \frac{r^3}{a'} \right) - 2a^2(R^2 + r^2) + 2(a''R + a'r) + 2Rr(a''r + a'R) + \\ & + 2Rr \left(\frac{a''}{a'} r^2 + \frac{a'}{a''} R^2 \right) - 2R^2r^2 \left(\frac{R}{a''} + \frac{r}{a'} \right) - 2Rr \left(\frac{R^2}{a''} \frac{r^2}{a'} + a''a' \right) - 2R^2r^2 + a^4 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Under certain assumptions, it is possible to obtain an analytical solution to the problem of the eccentricity of spherical bodies.

For the surfaces temperature difference, we write

$$\Delta t = \frac{Q}{4\pi\lambda} \left(\frac{1}{r_m'} - \frac{1}{r_m''} + \frac{1}{r_M'} - \frac{1}{r_M''} \right). \quad (6)$$

Taking into account the inequality (Fig.)

$$\frac{1}{r_m'} - \frac{1}{r_m''} + \frac{1}{r_M'} - \frac{1}{r_M''} > \frac{1}{r_m'} - \frac{1}{r_M'}, \quad (7)$$

and taking into account that $r_m'' \gg r_m'$ and $r_M'' \gg r_M'$

, and fractions $\frac{1}{r_m''}$, $\frac{1}{r_M''}$ have opposite signs, we can make the first assumption:

$$\Delta t = \frac{Q}{4\pi\lambda} \left(\frac{1}{r_m'} - \frac{1}{r_M'} \right). \quad (8)$$

Since the temperatures over the entire surface of the first and second spheres are the same

$$\frac{1}{r_m'} - \frac{1}{r_m''} = \frac{1}{r_n'} - \frac{1}{r_n''}, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{1}{r_M'} - \frac{1}{r_M''} = \frac{1}{r_N'} - \frac{1}{r_N''}, \quad (10)$$

or

$$r_n'' - r_m'' = (r_n' - r_m') \cdot \frac{r_m'' r_n''}{r_m' r_n'}, \quad (11)$$

$$r_N'' - r_M'' = (r_N' - r_M') \cdot \frac{r_M'' r_N''}{r_M' r_N'}. \quad (12)$$

It is also seen from the figure that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a'' - a' &= a \\ H - h &= a \\ 2h &= a' + \sqrt{\frac{r^3}{a'} + r^2 - a'r} \\ 2H &= a'' + \sqrt{\frac{R^3}{a''} + R^2 - a''R} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

For the joint solution of the last three equations, we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} r_n'' - r_m'' &= 2r \\ r_N'' - r_M'' &= 2R \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

Where

$$\frac{r_n'' - r_m''}{r_N'' - r_M''} = \frac{r}{R}. \quad (14)$$

From (11) and (12)

$$\frac{r_n'' - r_m''}{r_N'' - r_M''} = \frac{r_n' - r_m'}{r_N' - r_M'} \cdot \frac{r_m'' r_M''}{r_m' r_M'} \cdot \frac{r_n'' r_N''}{r_n' r_N'}. \quad (15)$$

Then the following inequalities can be written:

$$\frac{r_m'' r_M''}{r_m' r_M'} \cdot \frac{r_n'' r_N''}{r_n' r_N'} > \left(\frac{r_m'' r_M''}{r_m' r_M'} \right)^2 > \left(\frac{r_M''}{r_m''} \right)^2 > \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^2. \quad (16)$$

Let's make the following second assumption:

$$\frac{r_m'' r_M''}{r_m' r_M'} \cdot \frac{r_n'' r_N''}{r_n' r_N'} = \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^2. \quad (17)$$

Comparing relations (14), (15) and (17) we obtain

$$\left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^3 \frac{r_n'' - r_m''}{r_N'' - r_M''} = 1. \quad (18)$$

From figure 1

$$\left. \begin{aligned} r_m' + a' &= r \\ r_M' + a'' &= R \\ r_n' - a' &= r \\ r_N' - a'' &= R \\ a''' - a'' &= a \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (19)$$

Using equation (19) from (18) we find

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a'' &= \frac{ar^3}{R^3 - r^3} \\ a''' &= \frac{aR^3}{R^3 - r^3} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (20)$$

Taking into account (40), the (8) can be written as

$$\lambda = \frac{Q}{4\pi\Delta t} \cdot \frac{(R-r)\left(1 - \frac{a}{R-r}\right)}{Rr\left(1 - \frac{aR^2}{R^3 - r^3}\right)\left(1 - \frac{ar^2}{R^3 - r^3}\right)} \quad (21)$$

From (21) for limiting cases we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t &= 0 \quad \text{at } a = R - r \\ \Delta t &= \frac{Q}{4\pi\lambda} \cdot \frac{R - r}{Rr} \quad \text{at } a = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The resulting expression (21) is very convenient for calculating the thermal conductivity coefficient, taking into account the eccentricity of the working surfaces of equipment.

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